

Social support and school engagement in adolescence: moderated mediation models of life satisfaction and school climate

Lorea Azpiazu^{*a}, Oihane Fernández-Lasarte^b, Naiara Escalante^b, Iker Izar-de-la-Fuente^b

^aDepartment of Developmental and Educational Psychology, University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), San Sebastian, Spain; ^bDepartment of Developmental and Educational Psychology, University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), Vitoria, Spain.

*Corresponding author information: Lorea Azpiazu Izaguirre. Oñati 3 Plaza, 20018 San Sebastian, Spain (lorea.azpiazu@ehu.eus).

Social support and school engagement in adolescence: moderated mediation models of life satisfaction and school climate

Little is known about the mediating and moderating mechanisms that underlie the relationship between social support and school engagement. The present study aims to analyze: (1) the mediating role of life satisfaction on the association between social support (from teachers and friends) and school engagement; and (2) the moderating role of school climate in the relationships which exist between social support, life satisfaction and school engagement. Participants were 1397 adolescents (12-16 years old). Analyses were performed using the PROCESSv.4 macro and SPSSv.27. The results reveal that life satisfaction fully mediates the influence of support from friends on school engagement, and partially mediates the predictive effect of support from teachers on that same variable, with the indirect effect of support from teachers being moderated by school climate. The theoretical and practical implications of these results are discussed.

Keywords: Support from teachers; Support from friends; Life satisfaction; School engagement; School climate.

Introduction

School Engagement

Positive Education is an emerging field of study that seeks to expand educational goals beyond merely reacting to and preventing distress, in order to include the promotion and enhancement of student well-being. Within this paradigm, *school engagement*, understood as students' behaviors, feelings and thoughts regarding their school (Fredricks et al., 2004), is viewed as a crucial factor for sociopersonal development and academic success (Korpershoek et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2019).

School engagement protects against poor academic performance and absenteeism (Wang et al., 2019) and is associated with finding and keeping a job during adulthood (Xing & Gordon, 2021). It is therefore important to determine which variables facilitate school engagement during a developmental stage characterized by its decrease (Engels et al., 2019) and to clarify the type of associations established between them, particularly *life satisfaction* (Rodríguez-Fernández et al., 2018), *social support* (Demir & Leyendecker, 2018) and *school climate* (Encina & Berger, 2021). Indeed, in this study, school climate will be considered as a possible moderator in the direct and indirect relationships between social support and school engagement via life satisfaction.

School Engagement and Life Satisfaction

Previous research has found associations between *life satisfaction* and students' subjective school experiences (Antaramian, 2020), with those with high levels of life satisfaction, referred to the cognitive judgment people make about how satisfied they feel with their lives (Diener et al., 2017), scoring higher for academic performance and engagement (Datu et al., 2017). School engagement can therefore be considered a key resource that is consolidated through high levels of satisfaction and subjective well-being

(Rodríguez-Fernández et al., 2018), since satisfaction and positive emotions are inherently adaptive and useful for building sociopersonal and academic resources such as school engagement (Denovan et al., 2020).

School Engagement and Social Support: The Mediating Role of Life Satisfaction

Likewise, research has verified that schools constitute one of the most important contexts for adolescent development (Demir & Leyendecker, 2018), where social interactions with teachers and peers take place and from whom students receive support, understanding *social support* as the individual's perception of feeling cared for, valued, loved and part of a social network with shared responsibilities (Cobb, 1976). Research has found that the social support linked to the school environment (support from teachers and friends) is fundamental to ensuring students' engagement at school (Demir & Leyendecker, 2018) and life satisfaction (Lee & Lee, 2020), since adolescents share common spaces with teachers and peers for long periods of time (Bronfenbrenner & Morris, 2007). Some studies have found that support from teachers has a stronger influence on school engagement (Fernández-Lasarte et al., 2020), whereas support from friends impacts more life satisfaction (Wahlström et al., 2021). However, other studies highlight the importance of support from teachers in fostering life satisfaction (Bi et al., 2021).

Previous studies have shown that support from teachers and friends directly influences students' academic engagement (Li et al., 2020), having a stronger effect even than the support provided by families (Bradley et al., 2021). However, fewer studies have taken the mediating effect of life satisfaction into account when analyzing this relationship (Moksnes et al., 2016). Support from teachers has been found to be a strong predictor of school engagement, even when mediated by other personal variables (Rodríguez-Fernández et al., 2016). Furthermore, some studies have found that support from friends continues to

have a direct influence on school engagement even when this relationship is mediated by life satisfaction (Hakimzadeh et al., 2016), although others report only an indirect influence (Rodríguez-Fernández et al., 2016). However, the scarcity of studies in this field and the contradictory nature of the results reported to date reveal the need to continue exploring the dynamics of these relationships.

The Moderating Role of School Climate

School experiences are crucial to molding development trajectories and ensuring students' short, medium and long-term well-being (Chen et al., 2021). Consequently, schools are considered a fundamental environment for adolescent socialization (Santos-Souza et al., 2020), with their tasks including the responsibility for ensuring an adequate school climate that will have a positive influence on socioemotional well-being (Chen et al., 2021) and academic success (Kiuru et al., 2020).

Although school climate has been described in a number of different ways (La Salle, 2018), one of the most commonly-used definitions refers to the quality and nature of school life (Cohen, 2013) in relation to interpersonal interactions, behavioral rules and feelings of safety (Bradshaw et al., 2014). School climate is considered one of the most important school contextual factors (Zynuddin et al., 2023) that reflects socialization processes and is related to a wide range of socio-emotional and educational results (McGiboney, 2023), among which social support provided by teachers and peers (Coyle et al. al., 2022), life satisfaction (Aldridge et al., 2020) and school engagement (Encina & Berger, 2021) stands out.

School climate is increasingly recognized as an ecological construct (Coyle et al., 2022). As such, depending on their physical, material, sociopersonal and institutional characteristics, schools may (to differing degrees) establish a climate that is beneficial to students (Long et al., 2020), since positive environments constitute scenarios conducive to

healthy psychological development (Gaxiola-Romero et al., 2020). In other words, a negative school climate may function as a risk factor, whereas a positive one may encourage more positive perceptions among students of their immediate, school-based support network (Coyle et al., 2022), creating atmospheres that in turn foster life satisfaction (Aldridge et al., 2020) and school engagement (Encina & Berger, 2021). Therefore, it makes sense to hypothesize that school climate will affect the magnitude of the associations mentioned above (support from teachers and friends, life satisfaction and school engagement), since the perception of respect, security and trust in the school environment could influence the way in which social support and life satisfaction are perceived and associated with school commitment.

Specifically, Yang et al. (2020) find that the school climate intensifies the associations between interpersonal relationships and school engagement, since students who claim to attend safe, fair schools also perceive greater support from their teachers and peers (Coyle et al., 2022). However, there is hardly any direct evidence of the moderating effect of the school climate on the relationship between social support and life satisfaction, and between life satisfaction and school involvement. Much of the research interested in the moderating role of school climate has been carried out under the theme of bullying (Yang et al., 2020). These investigations show school climate as a factor that intensifies the relationships between victimization and school involvement (Yang et al., 2020). Way et al. (2007), although they study related variables, find that as the perception of the quality of the school climate decreases, so does the support of teachers and friends, as well as their psychological and behavioral adaptation. Wang et al. (2020) also find that the school climate intensifies the negative relationship established between companionship and depressive symptoms, since the effect is greater among adolescents who perceive a positive school climate. Consequently, it is evident the need to verify the moderating role of school climate in a dynamic of

relationships of positive psychological variables of which multivariate studies are hardly found.

The Preset Study

In light of the above, the aim of the present study is to test the theoretical models proposed in Figure 1, which establish mediations moderated by school climate in the associations between support from teachers and friends, life satisfaction and school engagement. Adolescence is a period in which school engagement often decreases (Engels et al., 2019), probably due to the many different academic challenges involved in compulsory education (Skinner et al., 2014). It is therefore important to understand which factors facilitate and moderate this construct, in order to design empirically-tested initiatives and interventions to improve it (Long et al., 2020). In pursuing this objective, the study aims to clarify: (a) whether life satisfaction fully or partially mediates the association between support from one's immediate school network (teachers and friends) and school engagement; (b) the degree to which the two types of support (from teachers and from friends) influence life satisfaction and school engagement; and (c) the nature of the moderating role played by school climate in the associations between support from teachers and friends, life satisfaction and school engagement.

Figure 1

Proposed theoretical models

Note. Continuous lines: simple mediation model; continuous and dotted lines: moderated mediation model.

Method

Participants

Participants were 1397 adolescents from both public (831 students) and semiprivate (566 students) schools (i.e., private schools that also receive some state funding) in the Autonomous Community of the Basque Country, in Spain. All were in compulsory secondary education and were aged between 12 and 16 years ($M = 13.88$; $SD = 1.27$). In terms of sex, 670 (48%) were men and 727 (52%) were women. The 13.7% of students perceived a high level of school climate, 69.2% perceived a medium level and 17.1% a low level. Respondents had no learning disabilities or other special needs. The families attending the schools had a mid-level socioeconomic and cultural status. The sample was recruited incidentally in accordance with the availability of the schools. The balance between public and semi-private schools and gender and age of the participants were accurately pursued.

Procedure

We contacted the management team of different schools to inform them of the objectives of this study. Once institutional participation was accepted, we sent a letter to the parents or legal guardians of the students in which the general objective of the study was specified and their informed consent was requested. Finally, 10 schools participated in the study. After, the data were collected in the different classrooms in sessions lasting approximately 40 minutes. The questionnaires were administered by members of the research team, who also informed students of the voluntary nature of their participation and the importance of being honest in their responses. In order to reduce the likelihood of social desirability bias and to avoid dishonest answers, they also assured them that their replies would be strictly confidential. The single blind criterion was used to mitigate participants' expectations and reactivity when completing the questionnaire, since the specific objectives

of the study were not revealed. The study complies with the ethical criteria established by the Ethical Commission in Research and Teaching (EID/IEEB) at the University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU).

Instruments

School climate and support from teachers were assessed using the *Perceptions of the School Environment* questionnaire (2006 Health Behavior in School-Aged Children study [HBSC] questionnaire adapted by Moreno et al., 2012), which assesses students' subjective view of their school context through two factors: *school climate*, referring to the support perceived from members of the school community, sense of belonging and rules (8 items; e.g.: "school rules are fair"); and *support from teachers*, referring to emotional and academic assistance and students' level of satisfaction with their teachers (8 items; e.g.: "our teachers are pleasant and friendly"). Items are rated on a 5-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 = *totally agree* to 5 = *totally disagree*. The reliability index obtained in this study was $\alpha = .817$, H coefficient = .830 and $IFC = .849$ for *school climate* and $\alpha = .846$, H coefficient = .855 and $IFC = .854$ for *support from teachers*.

Support from friends was measured using a 7-item subscale from the *Perceived Social Support from Family and Friends Questionnaire* (AFA; González-Ramírez & Landero, 2014). In this questionnaire, items are rated on a 5-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 = *never* to 5 = *always*. The subscale used in the present study assesses peers' willingness to talk and provide help, affection and support; it also measures respondents' satisfaction with the support received ("do you feel satisfied with the support you received from your friends?"). The reliability index obtained in this study was $\alpha = .828$, H coefficient = .876 and $IFC = .864$.

Life satisfaction was measured using the *Satisfaction with Life Scale* (SWLS; Diener et al., 1985), validated in Spanish by Atienza et al. (2000). This scale comprises 5 items that

measure respondents' overall cognitive appraisals of their life cycle ("In most ways my life is close to my ideal"). Items are rated on a 7-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 = *strongly disagree* to 7 *strongly agree*. The reliability index obtained in this study was $\alpha = .826$, H coefficient = .858 and $IFC = .837$.

School engagement was measured using the *School Engagement Measure* (Fredricks et al., 2005), validated in Spanish by Ramos-Díaz et al. (2016). The instrument comprises 16 items rated on a 5-point Likert-type scale ranging from 1 = *never* to 5 = *always*, and measures respondents' behavioral, emotional and cognitive appraisal of their school engagement through three factors: *behavioral engagement* (5 items; "I pay attention in class"); *emotional engagement* (6 items; "I feel happy in school"); and *cognitive engagement* (8 items; "I study at home even when I don't have a test"). The following reliability indexes were obtained in this study: *behavioral engagement*: $\alpha = .753$, H coefficient = .800 and $IFC = .755$; *emotional engagement*: $\alpha = .763$, H coefficient = .842 and $IFC = .817$; and *cognitive engagement*: $\alpha = .779$, H coefficient = .792 and $IFC = .775$.

Data Analysis

Missing values (2.1%) were calculated using the expectation maximization (EM) algorithm and Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC), both offered by the LISREL 8.8 program. A total of 273 outliers were eliminated with the SAS program, so the final base was 1397 participants without missing values. Normality, together with assumptions required in this type of analysis (Field, 2009; Hayes, 2018), was studied by means of scatter plots, P-P and Q-Q plots and was observed that the data fit the diagonal line with a fair degree of accuracy. Despite the fact that the P-P diagram shows a small deviation, the regression is robust against non-serious violations of normality (Hayes, 2018) and the kurtosis of each item has not exceeded the range $[\pm 3]$ (Salman et al., 2021). In consequence, the study of the

data set shows the feasibility of proceeding to the analysis of moderated mediation models (Clement et al., 2022). The descriptive data were calculated, along with the partial correlation matrix using the Pearson correlation coefficient.

To analyze mediation, model 4 of Hayes' PROCESSv.4 macro (2018) was used, following the steps established by Zhao et al. (2010). All effects were calculated using the Bootstrap technique for 10,000 samples, with a confidence interval of 95%. To analyze moderated mediation, we used model 59 of the PROCESSv.4 macro (Hayes, 2018). The variables were standardized and centered on the mean to facilitate the interpretation of the results. Conditional effects were established in accordance with high, medium and low positive school climate levels (1 SD under the mean and 1 SD above the mean). The pairwise contrast was used to compare the indirect effects of the different levels of the moderator and, in consequence, assess the existence of possible moderated mediation. All the analyses were carried out using the SPSS 27.0 statistical package.

Results

Mediation Analyses

After confirming that all the variables were positively and significantly associated (Table 1), we analyzed the mediation effect of life satisfaction using model 4 of the PROCESS macro (Hayes, 2018).

Table 1
Descriptive and correlational analyses

	2	3	4	5	Skewness	Kurtosis	M(sd)
1. Support/friends	.116***	.217***	.096***	.124***	-.967	1.005	28.30 (4.48)
2. Support/teachers		.260***	.438***	.689***	-.378	.395	26.30 (5.87)
3. Life satisfaction			.366***	.328***	-.887	.720	26.20 (5.63)
4. School engagement				.546***	.034	-.042	64.33 (9.82)
5. School climate					-.353	-.048	27.58 (5.49)

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

Table 2 shows the results referred to model 4 Process, according to which the

influence of *teacher support* on *school engagement* is mediated by *life satisfaction*. The results in Table 2 show the direct influence of *teacher support* on *life satisfaction* and *school engagement*, as well as the direct influence of *life satisfaction* on *school engagement*. It is also observed that the effect size of *teacher support* on *life satisfaction* is relatively low ($R^2 = .067$) while *teacher support* and *life satisfaction* has a larger effect size on *school engagement* ($R^2 = .260$), although it also remains relatively low. The results also reveal the existence of an indirect effect of *teacher support* on *school engagement* through *life satisfaction* ($\beta = .070$, $SE = .010$, 95% CI [.052, .090]) and a total effect of $\beta = .438$ ($SE = .040$, 95% CI [.653, .811]) in 10.000 Bootstrap samples. Consequently, the results seem to indicate the existence of complementary partial mediation, given that the indirect effect and the direct effect are significant and point in the same direction (Zhao et al., 2010).

Table 2
Simple mediation model 1

Predictive variable	Life satisfaction (MV)				School engagement (DV)			
	β	SE	95% CI		β	SE	95% CI	
Support/teachers (IV)	.260	.029	.194	.306	.368	.046	.522	.704
Life satisfaction					.271	.048	.379	.566
R	.260				.510			
R^2	.067				.260			
$F(df_1, df_2)$	101.035*** (1, 1397)				245.679*** (2, 1396)			

Note. IV = Independent variable; MV = mediating variable; DV = dependent variable; Model 1 = referring to the influence of *teacher support* on *school engagement* mediated by *life satisfaction* (macro process model 4); * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

Table 3 shows the results referred to model 4 Process according to which the influence of *support from friends* on *school engagement* is mediated by *life satisfaction*. The results show the direct influence of *support from friends* on *life satisfaction*, as well as the direct influence of *life satisfaction* on *school engagement*. The results also indicate that the effect size of *support from friends* on *life satisfaction* is relatively low ($R^2 = .047$) while *support from friends* and *life satisfaction* has a larger effect size on *school engagement* ($R^2 = .134$). The results also reveal the existence of an indirect effect of *support from friends* on *school engagement* through *life satisfaction* ($\beta = .079$, $SE = .012$, 95% CI [.056, .104]) and a

total effect ($\beta = .096$, $SE = .058$, 95% CI [.096, .325]) in 10.000 Bootstrap samples.

Consequently, although with a relatively small magnitude, the results seem to indicate the existence of indirect mediation or total mediation, since the indirect effect is significant, but not the direct effect (Zhao et al., 2010).

Table 3
Simple mediation model 2

	Life satisfaction (MV)				School engagement (DV)			
	β	SE	95% CI		β	SE	95% CI	
			LL	UL			LL	UL
Support/friend (IV)	.217	.037	.199	.346	.017	.061	-.080	.158
Life satisfaction					.362	.050	.535	.729
<i>R</i>	.217				.367			
<i>R</i> ²	.047				.134			
<i>F</i> (<i>df</i> ₁ , <i>df</i> ₂)	68.810*** (1,1397)				108.379*** (2, 1396)			

Note. IV = Independent variable; MV = mediating variable; DV = dependent variable; *Model 2* = referring to the influence of *friend support* on *school engagement* mediated by *life satisfaction* (macro process model 4); * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

Moderated Mediation

Two model 59 were run in the PROCESS macro (Hayes, 2018) to test whether the simple mediation models were moderated by *school climate* (Tables 4 and 6). Table 4 presents a summary of the model for the association between *support from teachers* and *school engagement*, through *life satisfaction* moderated by *school climate*. As evidenced by Table 4, the results show that *teacher support* and *school climate* explain 11.9% of the variance of *life satisfaction* and that the three variables (*teacher support*, *school climate* and *life satisfaction*) explain 35.9% of *school engagement*.

Table 4

Summary of the model for the association between support from teachers and school engagement, through life satisfaction moderated by school climate

Predictive variable	Life satisfaction (MV)				School engagement (DV)			
	β	SE	95% CI		β	SE	95% CI	
			LL	UL			LL	UL
Support from teachers	.079	.036	.009	.150	.117	.033	.051	.182
School climate	.289	.035	.221	.356	.413	.033	.348	.478
Support from teachers*School climate	.080	.025	.028	.127	.083	.020	.044	.120
Life satisfaction	-	-	-	-	.208	.027	.156	.262
Life satisfaction*School climate	-	-	-	-	.051	.022	.007	.096
	R	.344			.599			
	R ²	.119			.359			
	F (df ₁ , df ₂)	62.551(3, 1395)***			155.797 (5, 1393)***			

Note. MV = mediating variable; DV = dependent variable. Results referring to model 1 of Figure 1 (Macro process 59). * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

The results reveal that *school climate* moderated the predictive power of *support from teachers* on *life satisfaction*; although the conditional effects indicated that this predictive power was only present when students perceived a medium ($\beta = .079$, $SE = .035$, 95% CI [.010, .147]) or high level of positive *school climate* ($\beta = .159$, $SE = .043$, 95% CI [.075, .243]), and was not found when the level perceived was low ($\beta = -.002$, $SE = .039$, 95% CI [-.078, .075]). The results also indicated that the association was stronger the higher the level of positive *school climate* perceived (Figure 2a).

School climate was also found to moderate the predictive power of *life satisfaction* on *school engagement* among students perceiving a low ($\beta = .158$, $SE = .027$, 95% CI [.104, .211]), medium ($\beta = .208$, $SE = .024$, 95% CI [.162, .255]) and high level of positive *school climate* ($\beta = .259$, $SE = .035$, 95% CI [.190, .328]), with this predictive power being stronger the higher the level of positive *school climate* perceived (Figure 2b).

As regards the direct effect of *support from teachers* on *school engagement*, the results revealed that this association was moderated by *school climate* when the perceived level of this variable was medium ($\beta = .117$, $SE = .030$, 95% CI [.058, .175]) or high ($\beta = .199$, $SE = .038$, 95% CI [.125, .273]); but not when it was low ($\beta = .034$, $SE = .033$, 95% CI [-.032, .099]). The results also revealed that the association was stronger the higher the level

of positive *school climate* perceived (Figure 2c).

Figure 2
Moderating effect

Finally, the results revealed that *life satisfaction* significantly mediated the association between *support from teachers* and *school engagement* when *school climate* was medium ($\beta = .016, SE = .008, 95\% CI [.002, .032]$) and high ($\beta = .041, SE = .012, 95\% CI [.019, .066]$), although not when it was low ($\beta = .000, SE = .007, 95\% CI [-.015, .014]$). Moreover, the pairwise contrast of indirect conditional effects confirmed that the indirect effect was moderated by *school climate* (Table 5). That is, it seems that the indirect effect of *teacher support* on *school engagement* is modified by *school climate* values.

Table 5
Pairwise testing of indirect conditional effects

<i>Effect 1</i>	<i>Effect 2</i>	<i>contrast</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>LLCI</i>	<i>ULCI</i>
.016	.000	.017	.005	.007	.027
.041	.000	.041	.012	.018	.066
.041	.016	.025	.008	.010	.041

Note. Effect 1 and Effect 2 refer to the indirect effect values chosen to compare each moderator level.

Table 6 presents a summary of the model for the association between *support from friends* and *school engagement*, through *life satisfaction* moderated by *school climate*. The results of this table show that *support from friends* and *school climate* explain 14.2% of *life satisfaction* and that the three variables (*support from friends*, *school climate* and *life satisfaction*) explain 20.6% of *school engagement*.

Table 6

Summary of the model for the association between support from friends and school engagement, through life satisfaction moderated by school climate

Predictive variable	Life satisfaction (MV)				School engagement (DV)			
	β	SE	95% CI		β	SE	95% CI	
Support from friends	.172	.028	.117	.226	-.011	.024	-.057	.036
School climate	.309	.028	.255	.364	.472	.025	.422	.521
Support/friends*School climate	-.052	.029	-.107	.005	-.032	.023	-.077	.015
Life satisfaction	-	-	-	-	.232	.027	.179	.286
Life satisfaction*School climate	-	-	-	-	.089	.023	.045	.136
<i>R</i>	.377				.454			
<i>R</i> ²	.142				.206			
<i>F</i> (<i>df</i> ₁ , <i>df</i> ₂)	76.803*** (3, 1395)				72.206*** (5, 1393)			

Note. MV = mediating variable; DV = dependent variable. Results referring to model 2 of Figure 1 (Macro process 59). * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$.

The results presented in Table 6 reveal that *school climate* did not moderate the predictive power of *support from friends* on *life satisfaction*, although this association between these two latter variables was found to be stronger among students who perceived a lower level of positive *school climate*.

School climate was found to moderate the association between *life satisfaction* and *school engagement* among students perceiving a low ($\beta = .142$, $SE = .028$, 95% CI [.087, .198]), medium ($\beta = .232$, $SE = .024$, 95% CI [.185, .279]) and high level of positive *school climate* ($\beta = .321$, $SE = .035$, 95% CI [.253, .389]). This association was stronger the better the *school climate* perceived (Figure 3).

Figure 3
Moderating effect of school climate on the association between life satisfaction and school engagement

Finally, the results revealed that *life satisfaction* significantly mediated the association between *support from friends* and *school engagement* when *school climate* was low ($\beta = .032$, $SE = .009$, 95% CI [.016, .052]), medium ($\beta = .040$, $SE = .008$, 95% CI [.026, .056]) and high ($\beta = .043$, $SE = .014$, 95% CI [.014, .065]). However, the pairwise contrast of indirect conditional effects failed to confirm that the indirect effect in question was moderated by *school climate* (Table 7).

Table 7
Pairwise testing of indirect conditional effects

<i>Effect 1</i>	<i>Effect 2</i>	<i>contrast</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>LLCI</i>	<i>ULCI</i>
.040	.032	.008	.007	-.006	.021
.039	.032	.007	.015	-.024	.037
.039	.040	-.001	.010	-.020	.018

Note. Effect 1 and Effect 2 refer to the indirect effect values chosen to compare each moderator level.

Discussion

Adolescence is a developmental stage in which school engagement often decreases (Engels et al., 2019), probably due to the many different academic challenges involved in compulsory education (Skinner et al., 2014). Many studies (Wang et al., 2019), including a meta-analysis by Korpershoek et al. (2020), have reported the benefits of good school

engagement for adolescents' academic and psychological development, which is why it is so important to identify its facilitating and moderating factors, in order to enable the design of effective initiatives and interventions designed to enhance it (Long et al., 2020). From the perspective of Positive Education, the aim of the present study was therefore to test two theoretical models of mediations moderated by school climate in the associations between support from teachers and friends, life satisfaction and school engagement.

Since the publication of the study by Moksnes et al. in 2016, increased interest has been expressed by the scientific community in exploring the psychosocial benefits of life satisfaction and understanding how it mediates between other variables. Despite the lack of previous research, the results of the present study indicate that life satisfaction mediates the predictive power of support from the school environment on school engagement. They also reveal that the indirect predictive effect of support from teachers is moderated by school climate, although the indirect predictive effect of support from friends is not. Furthermore, the type of mediation (full or partial) varies in accordance with the source of support, with support from teachers having a stronger effect on school engagement and academic outcomes (Fernández-Lasarte et al., 2020), and support from friends having a stronger influence on life satisfaction (Wahlström et al., 2021). Southwick et al. (2014) found that one's perception of the support available may change in accordance with source, type and need.

The model referring to support from teachers (Figure 1, Model 1) indicates that life satisfaction partially mediates the association between support from teachers and school engagement (Demir & Leyendecker, 2018). Given that adolescent students may want and perceive support from different sources in accordance with their specific needs (Southwick et al., 2014), the results of our study suggest that although teachers do influence life satisfaction (Bi et al., 2021), their presence is more directly relevant for generating psychological bonds

with the school (Rodríguez-Fernández et al., 2016), since they are responsible for establishing an environment that may significantly affect students' psychological experiences in terms of learning and social interactions (Lee & Lee, 2020). Teachers provide instrumental and informational support through explanations and tasks designed to facilitate access to academic content (Martin & Dowson, 2009), as well as by modeling acceptable behavioral and emotional conduct and offering emotional support (Tvedt et al., 2021).

For its part, the model referring to support from friends (Figure 1, Model 2) reveals the total mediation of life satisfaction in the association between this variable and school engagement. Although the family remains an important source of support during adolescence, it is during this period that friends become particularly relevant (Bonnie et al., 2015). Although research has found that, under ideal circumstances, friends provide emotional support, act as positive role models and help adolescents understand and complete school tasks (Bradley et al., 2021), it seems that, more than directly affecting school engagement, they do so indirectly through life satisfaction (Bi et al., 2021), due to the intrinsic importance acquired by the peer group during adolescence. If teenagers feel happy and content, they are likely to enjoy their time at school more and to view it as a pleasant place to be, circumstances that lead to stronger feelings of psychological connection with it (Osterman, 2000). Indeed, the results of the present study indicate the key role played by life satisfaction in both models, highlighting the importance of adolescents feeling happy and satisfied in order to be able to establish positive connections in the school environment in which they interact (Rodríguez-Fernández et al., 2018).

School climate has a strong influence on socioemotional well-being (Chen et al., 2021) and academic success (Kiuru et al., 2020), and is directly derived from the educational environment, which is why it is considered to have a potential moderating effect on the

association between the social interactions that take place at school, psychological variables and school engagement (Yang et al., 2020). However, few studies have sought to explore this possibility, and most of those that have focus on the issue of school bullying (Zacharia & Yablon, 2022). The results reported here regarding the moderating effect of school climate on the associations included in the models studied are therefore of particular interest.

In accordance with Gaxiola-Romero et al. (2020), who argue that positive environments constitute scenarios of sustainable transactions in which people receive and obtain benefits, the results of the present study show that in a positive school environment, life satisfaction facilitates school engagement and the relationships established with teachers also help foster this feeling (Yang et al., 2020), although this last association was not found among students who perceive a weak, school climate (Thomas et al., 2019). This serves to highlight the importance of establishing a positive climate at school, since better perceptions of school climate encourage students to view the help provided by teachers as a positive asset, thereby generating stronger feelings of commitment to the school and intensifying the existing association between life satisfaction and school engagement.

The present study also found that school climate intensifies the association between support from teachers and life satisfaction, although it does not seem to moderate the effect of support from friends on this same variable. Moreover, the data show that this last interaction fails to reach significance level. The results therefore indicate, once again, that support can have different benefits for adolescent development depending on its source. Although it is true that support from teachers enhances adolescent life satisfaction (Bi et al., 2021), it is also true that the student-teacher relationship is constructed in accordance with the rules and educational and social values predominant at the school (Bradshaw et al., 2014), since teachers' expectations and the fairness of the rules and consistency with which they are

enforced characterize the structure of the school environment (La Salle, 2018). Those who see themselves as positively involved in the school context tend to share and understand the values and rules of their school and perceive the help provided by teachers more easily, which in turn has a stronger impact on how satisfied they feel with their lives. In light of the above, it makes sense for the indirect effect of support from teachers on school engagement to be moderated by school climate.

However, the effect of support from friends on life satisfaction does not appear to vary in accordance with this variable. The importance of friends during adolescence is an intrinsic characteristic of this developmental stage (Bonnie et al., 2015), in which social acceptance and peer support are considered fundamental for ensuring well-being (Wahlström et al., 2021), perhaps even regardless of school rules and the type of school in which peer relations are established. The negative association found in this sense suggests that, in more adverse educational environments, friendships become particularly important to ensuring well-being, since they provide support in potentially threatening development processes, such as individuation from parents, identity development and adaptation to possible stressful environments (Lee & Lee, 2020). Studies analyzing conflictive environments have found that such climates weaken the association between social networks and well-being (Paluck et al., 2019). It is therefore important to analyze this finding in more diverse school contexts, particularly in schools with high levels of interpersonal conflict.

The present study has a number of limitations that should be taken into consideration. Firstly, it analyzes two moderated mediation models separately. Future studies may wish to analyze the support provided by both sources together, using latent variables and specifying the type of support provided (emotional, instrumental or informational), since this will enable a better understanding of the associations established between the variables under study.

Secondly, the results were obtained from a small sample of secondary school students. Future studies may wish to broaden the sample to include populations outside this age range (primary school, Spanish Bacalaureate and university students, for example), and to recruit them from a more varied range of schools. It would also be useful for future studies to analyze whether the results found in the present study hold as a function of gender, age and school, since previous studies have found differences in school engagement as a function of age and gender in favor of the youngest female group (Santos et al., 2021) or type of school in favor of smaller (Fullarton, 2002) and respectful of students' rights schools (Covell, 2010). A third limitation is linked to the fact that the sample was chosen incidentally, being more appropriate the use of a random sampling. Similarly, despite the large sample size, when generalizing the results of this study, it should be taken into account that it is not representative of all socioeconomic realities, since it has focused on the middle-class population. In addition, future studies could expand the results of this research by analyzing the socioeconomic level as a strange variable with a possible influence on the perception of social support among peers. Finally, the cross-sectional nature of the study limits its capacity to explore dependency between the variables. Consequently, future experimental designs should seek to empirically confirm the data reported here.

Conclusions

The findings reported in the present study highlight the key role played by teachers and friends in school engagement, as well as the important influence of life satisfaction on this same variable and the necessity of fostering a positive school climate in order to intensify these associations.

In terms of research contributions, this study analyzes a series of relationships that required further scientific inquiry and provides valuable information for the development of future research, such as the analysis of the relationships between the variables under study,

taking into account socioeconomic level, age, gender and school. The educational models tested also serve as a relevant cue to be analyzed through longitudinal designs.

This research can also help teachers and researchers to know more accurately how adolescent students perceive school engagement and identify the aspects that can be improved to favor a positive school adaptation, to work on the development of these aspects, such as social support, life satisfaction and school climate, and to provide clearer educational guidelines to address them. Therefore, the results obtained here have a significant practical value for the design of future educational interventions, showing in a generic way the interrelation between different variables for the promotion of other school adjustment variables during adolescence.

The findings have serious practical implications, since they prompt us to consider the importance of developing institutional, organizational and interpersonal strategies designed to establish a good school climate in order to strengthen the associations found. Given that school climate is considered an evidence-based strategy for school improvement, it is important for students and educational professionals to learn and work together to create safer, more supportive and more attractive schools (Encina & Berger, 2021).

For this purpose, it would be convenient to use several courses of action and to use an approach that allows to (Sánchez et al., 2006): (a) analyze and make improvements in the school curriculum and introduce changes in the form of programs in the regular curriculum with the potential participation of families; (b) propose environmental modifications, using the school's own resources in a systematic and organized way, and promote improvements such as open classrooms, cooperative classroom organization, peer tutoring, student leagues, etc.; (c) promote teacher training, involving them in the implementation and monitoring of programs to increase their professional effectiveness and providing them with new resources that their teaching performance would give.

The findings presented here may therefore contribute to designing school programs, taking into account the avenues of action indicated, that seek to foster the engagement and participation of students in their school through the establishment of bonds that foster the development of a stronger perception of social support and increase adolescent life satisfaction. A direct action and one that could be incorporated into the regular school curriculum could be the expression of gratitude and interventions focused on students' strengths (Howel et al., 2013). For example, Froh et al. (2008) randomly assigned students to either identify (on a daily basis for 2 weeks) things for which they were grateful, to identify things they found annoying, or to do nothing. Expressing gratitude was related to outcomes such as life satisfaction, interpersonal relationships and students' school engagement, among other outcomes (such as optimism, enthusiasm, etc.). Likewise, it would be advisable to implement interventions to improve self-esteem in adolescent students, which could lead to greater personal and school well-being (Coelho et al., 2020).

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author, [*details removed for blind review*]. The data are not publicly available due to privacy of research participants and ethical restrictions.

References

- Aldridge, J. M., & McChesney, K. (2018). The relationships between school climate and adolescent mental health and wellbeing: A systematic literature review. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 88, 121-145. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2018.01.012>
- Aldridge, J. M., McChesney, K., & Afari, E. (2020). Associations between school climate and student life satisfaction: Resilience and bullying as mediating factors. *Learning Environments Research*, 23, 129-150. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10984-019-09296-9>
- Antaramian, S. P. (2020). Life satisfaction. In S. Hupp and J. D. Jewell (Eds.), *The encyclopedia of child and adolescent development* (pp. 1-10.). John Wiley & Sons, Inc. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119171492.wecad346>
- Atienza, F., Pons, D., Balaguer, I., & García-Merita, M. (2000). Propiedades psicométricas de la escala de satisfacción con la vida en adolescentes [Psychometric properties of life satisfaction scale in adolescents]. *Psicothema*, 12(2), 314-319.
- Berns, R. M. (2015). *Child, family, school, community: Socialization and support*. Cengage Learning.
- Bi, S., Stevens, G. W., Maes, M., Boer, M., Delaruelle, K., Eriksson, C., Brooks, F. M., Tesler, R., van der Schuur, W. A., & Finkenauer, C. (2021). Perceived social support from different sources and adolescent life satisfaction across 42 countries/regions: The moderating role of national-level generalized trust. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 50, 1384-1409. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-021-01441-z>
- Bonnie, R. J., Stroud, C., & Breiner, H., (2015). *Young adults in the 21st century. In investing in the health and well-being of young adults*. National Academies Press.
- Bradley, G. L., Ferguson, S., & Zimmer-Gembeck, M. J. (2021). Parental support, peer support and school connectedness as foundations for student engagement and academic achievement in

Australian youth. In R. Dimitrova and N. Wiium (Eds.), *Handbook of positive youth development* (pp. 219-236). Springer.

Bradshaw, C. P., Waasdorp, T. E., Debnam, K. J., & Johnson, S. L. (2014). Measuring school climate in high schools: A focus on safety, engagement, and the environment. *Journal of School Health, 84*(9), 593-604. <https://doi.org/10.1111/josh.12186>

Bronfenbrenner, U., & Morris, P. A. (2007). The bioecological model of human development. In W. Damon and R. M. Lerner (Eds.), *Handbook of child psychology: Theoretical models of human development* (pp. 793-828). John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/9780470147658.chpsy0114>

Chen, Y., Hinton, C., & VanderWeele, T. J. (2021). School types in adolescence and subsequent health and well-being in young adulthood: An outcome-wide analysis. *PLoS ONE, 16*(11), Article e0258723. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0258723>

Clement, L. M., & Bradley-Garcia, M. (2022). A step-by-step tutorial for performing a moderated mediation analysis using PROCESS. *The Quantitative Methods for Psychology, 18*(3), 258-271. <http://doi.org/10.20982/tqmp.18.3.p258>

Cobb, S. (1976). Social support as a moderator of life stress. *Psychosomatic Medicine, 38*(5), 300-314. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00006842-197609000-00003>

Coelho, V. A., Bear, G. G., & Brás, P. (2020). A multilevel analysis of the importance of school climate for the trajectories of students' self-concept and self-esteem throughout the middle school transition. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence, 49*(9), 1793-1804.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-020-01245-7>

Cohen, J. (2013). Creating a positive school climate: A foundation for resilience. In S. Goldstein (Ed.), *Handbook of resilience in children* (pp. 411-423). Springer.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4614-3661-4>

- Covell, K. (2010). School engagement and rights-respecting schools. *Cambridge Journal of Education*, 40(1), 39-51. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03057640903567021>
- Coyle, S., Weinreb, K. S., Davila, G., & Cuellar, M. (2022). Relationships matter: The protective role of teacher and peer support in understanding school climate for victimized youth. *Child & Youth Care Forum*, 51, 181-203. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10566-021-09620-6>
- Datu, J. A. D., Valdez, J. P., Cabrera, I. K., & Salanga, M. G. (2017). Subjective happiness optimizes educational outcomes: Evidence from Filipino high school students. *The Spanish Journal of Psychology*, 20, Article E60. <https://doi.org/10.1017/sjp.2017.55>
- Demir, M., & Leyendecker, B. (2018). School-related social support is associated with school engagement, self-competence and health-related quality of life (HRQoL) in Turkish immigrant students. *Frontiers in Education*, 3, Article 83. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2018.00083>
- Denovan, A., Dagnall, N., Macaskill, A., & Papageorgiou, K. (2020). Future time perspective, positive emotions and student engagement: A longitudinal study. *Studies in Higher Education*, 45(7), 1533-1546. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03075079.2019.1616168>
- Diener, E., Emmons, R. A., Larsen, R. J., & Griffin, S. (1985). The satisfaction with life scale. *Journal of Personality Assessment*, 49(1), 71-75. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327752jpa4901_13
- Diener, E., Heintzelman, S. J., Kushlev, K., Tay, L., Wirtz, D., Lutes, L. D., & Oishi, S. (2017). Findings all psychologists should know from the new science on subjective well-being. *Canadian Psychology*, 58(2), 87-104. <http://doi.org/doi:10.1037/cap0000063>
- Duncheon, J. C. (2020). "We are exposed to that college environment": Exploring the socialization of early college high school students. *Community College Review*, 48(2), 173-194. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0091552119898880>

- Encina, Y., & Berger, C. (2021). Civic behavior and sense of belonging at school: The moderating role of school climate. *Child Indicators Research, 14*, 1453-1477.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12187-021-09809-0>
- Engels, M. C., Colpin, H., Wouters, S., Van Leeuwen, K., Bijttebier, P., Van Den Noortgate, W., Goossens, L., & Verschueren, K. (2019). Adolescents' peer status profiles and differences in school engagement and loneliness trajectories: A person-centered approach. *Learning and Individual Differences, 72*, Article 101759. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2019.101759>
- Fernández-Lasarte, O., Ramos-Díaz, E., Goñi, E., & Rodríguez-Fernández, A. (2020). The role of social support in school adjustment during secondary education. *Psicothema, 32*(1), 100-107.
<https://doi.org/10.7334/psicothema2019.125>
- Field, A. (2009). *Discovering statistics using IBM SPSS statistics* (3ed edition). Sage Publications.
- Fredricks, J. A., Blumenfeld, P. C., Friedel, J., & Paris, A. (2005). School engagement. In K. A. Moore and L. H. Lippman (Eds.), *What do children need to flourish: Conceptualizing and measuring indicators of positive development* (pp. 305-321). Springer.
https://doi.org/10.1007/0-387-23823-9_19
- Fredricks, J. A., Blumenfeld, P. C., & Paris, A. H. (2004). School engagement: Potential of the concept, state of the evidence. *Review of Educational Research, 74*(1), 59-109.
<https://doi.org/10.3102/00346543074001059>
- Froh, J. J., Sefick, W. J., & Emmons, R. A. (2008). Counting blessings in early adolescents: An experimental study of gratitude and subjective well-being. *Journal of School Psychology, 46*, 213-233. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsp.2007.03.005>
- Fullarton, S. (2002). *Student engagement with school: Individual and school-level influences*. Australian Council for Educational Research.
- Gaxiola-Romero, J. C., Gaxiola-Villa, E., Corral-Frías, N. S., & Escobedo-Hernández, P. (2020). Positive learning environment, academic engagement and self-regulated learning in high

school students. *Acta Colombiana de Psicología*, 23(2), 267-278.

<https://doi.org/10.14718/acp.2020.23.2.11>

González-Ramírez, M. T., & Landero, R. (2014). Propiedades psicométricas de la escala de Apoyo social Familiar y de Amigos (AFA-R) en una muestra de estudiantes [Psychometric properties of the Family and Friends Social Support scale (AFA-R) in a students sample].

Acta de Investigación Psicológica, 4(2), 1469-1480. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s2007-4719\(14\)70387-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s2007-4719(14)70387-4)

Hakimzadeh, R., Besharat, M. A., Khaleghinezhad, S. A., & Ghorban Jahromi, R. (2016). Peers' perceived support, student engagement in academic activities and life satisfaction: A structural equation modeling approach. *School Psychology International*, 37(3), 240-254.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0143034316630020>

Hayes, A. (2018). *Introduction to mediation, moderation, and conditional process analysis: A regression-based approach* (2 edition). Guilford Press.

Health Behavior in School-Aged Children study [HBSC]. (2008). *Health Behaviour in School-aged Children (HBSC) study: International report from the 2005/06 survey*. World Health Organization.

Howell, A. J., Keyes, C. L., & Passmore, H. A. (2013). Flourishing among children and adolescents: Structure and correlates of positive mental health, and interventions for its enhancement. In C. Proctor and P. A. Linley (Eds.). *Research, applications, and interventions for children and adolescents* (pp. 59-79). Springer.

Kiuru, N., Wang, M. T., Salmela-Aro, K., Kannas, L., Ahonen, T., & Hirvonen, R. (2020).

Associations between adolescents' interpersonal relationships, school well-being, and academic achievement during educational transitions. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 49(5), 1057-1072. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-019-01184-y>

- Korpershoek, H., Canrinus, E. T., Fokkens-Bruinsma, M., & de Boer, H. (2020). The relationships between school belonging and students' motivational, social-emotional, behavioural, and academic outcomes in secondary education: A meta-analytic review. *Research Papers in Education*, 35(6), 641-680. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02671522.2019.1615116>
- La Salle, T. P. (2018). International perspectives of school climate. *School Psychology International*, 39(6), 559-567. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0143034318808336>
- Lee, M., & Lee, S. M. (2020). Teacher and peer relationships and life satisfaction: Mediating the role of student resilience in south Korean elementary schools. *Journal of Psychologists and Counsellors in Schools*, 33(1), 13-25. <https://doi.org/10.1017/jgc.2020.21>
- Li, W., Gao, W., & Sha, J. (2020). Perceived teacher autonomy support and school engagement of Tibetan students in elementary and middle schools: Mediating effect of self-efficacy and academic emotions. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, Article 50. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2020.00050>
- Long, E., Zucca, C., & Sweeting, H. (2020). School climate, peer relationships, and adolescent mental health: A social ecological perspective. *Youth and Society*, 53(8), 1400-1415. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0044118X20970232>
- Martin, A.J., & Dowson, M. (2009). Interpersonal relationships, motivation, engagement, and achievement: Yields for theory, current issues, and practice. *Review of Educational Research*, 79(1), 327-365. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0034654308325583>
- McGiboney, G. W. (2023). *The psychology of school climate*. Cambridge Scholars Publishing.
- Moksnes, U. K., Løhre, A., Lillefjell, M., Byrne, D. G., & Haugan, G. (2016). The association between school stress, life satisfaction and depressive symptoms in adolescents: Life satisfaction as a potential mediator. *Social Indicators Research*, 125(1), 339-357. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-014-0842-0>

- Moreno, C, Ramos-Valverde, P., Rivera, F., Muñoz-Tinoco, V., Sánchez-Queija, I., Granado, M. C., & Jiménez-Iglesias, A. (2012). *Desarrollo adolescente y salud en España: Resumen del estudio Health Behaviour in School Aged Children (HBSC-2006)* [Adolescent development and health in Spain: Summary of the study Health Behavior in School Aged Children (HBSC-2006)]. Ministerio de Sanidad, Política Social e Igualdad.
- Osterman, K. F. (2000). Students' need for belonging in the school community. *Review of Educational Research, 70*(3), 323-367. <https://doi.org/10.3102/00346543070003323>
- Paluck, E. L., Shepherd, H., & Aronow, P. M. (2019). Changing climates of conflict: A social network experiment in 56 schools. *PNAS, 113*(3), 566-571. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1821346116>
- Ramos-Díaz, E., Rodríguez-Fernández, A., & Revuelta, L. (2016). Validation of the Spanish version of the School Engagement Measure (SEM). *The Spanish Journal of Psychology, 19*(86), 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1017/sjp.2016.94>
- Rodríguez-Fernández, A., Ramos-Díaz, E., & Axpe, I. (2018). The role of resilience and psychological well-being in school engagement and perceived academic performance: An exploratory model to improve academic achievement. In B. Bernal-Morales (Ed.), *Health and academic achievement* (pp. 159-176). Intechopen. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.73580>
- Rodríguez-Fernández, A., Ramos-Díaz, E., Fernández-Zabala, A., Goñi, E., Esnaola, I., & Goñi, A. (2016). Contextual and psychological variables in a descriptive model of subjective well-being and school engagement. *International Journal of Clinical and Health Psychology, 16*(2), 166-174. <http://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijchp.2016.01.003>
- Salman, M., Khan, B., Khan, S. Z., & Khan, R. U. (2021). The impact of heuristic availability bias on investment decision-making: Moderated mediation model. *Business Strategy & Development, 4*(3), 246-257. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bsd2.148>

- Sánchez, A. M., Rivas, M. T., & Trianes, M. V. (2006). Eficacia de un programa de intervención para la mejora del clima escolar: algunos resultados. *Electronic Journal of Research in Education Psychology*, 4(9), 353-370. <https://doi.org/10.25115/ejrep.v4i9.1197>
- Santos, A. C., Simões, C., Cefai, C., Freitas, E., & Arriaga, P. (2021). Emotion regulation and student engagement: Age and gender differences during adolescence. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 109, Article 101830. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2021.101830>
- Santos-Souza, D. F., Ferreira de Jesús, T., & Noll, M. (2020). Family and school context: Effects on the mental health of Brazilian students. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(17), Article 6042. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17176042>
- Skinner, E. A., Pitzer, J., & Brule, H. (2014). The role of emotion in engagement, coping, and the development of motivational resilience. In R. Pekrun and L. Linnenbrink-Garcia (Eds.), *International handbook of emotions in education* (pp. 331-347). Routledge.
- Southwick, S. M., Bonanno, G. A., Masten, A. S., Panter-Brick, C., & Yehuda, R. (2014). Resilience definitions, theory and challenges: Interdisciplinary perspectives. *European Journal of Psychotraumatology*, 5, 1-14. <http://doi.org/10.3402/ejpt.v5.25338>
- Thomas, K. J., Moreira de Cunha, J., Americo de Souza, D., & Santo, J. (2019). Fairness, trust, and school climate as foundational to growth mindset: A study among Brazilian children and adolescents. *Educational Psychology*, 39(4), 510-529. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01443410.2018.1549726>
- Tvedt, M. S., Bru, E., & Idsoe, T. (2021). Perceived teacher support and intentions to quit upper secondary school: Direct, and indirect associations via emotional engagement and boredom. *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research*, 65(1), 101-122. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00313831.2019.1659401>
- Wahlström, J., Låftman, S. B., Modin, B., & Löfstedt, P. (2021). Psychosocial working conditions in school and life satisfaction among adolescents in Sweden: A cross-sectional study.

International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, 18(10), Article 5337.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s41042-019-00017-4>

Wang, Z., Liu, C., Li, T., & Zhao, F. (2020). Paternal parenting and depressive symptoms among adolescents: A moderated mediation model of deviant peer affiliation and school climate.

Children and Youth Services Review, 119, Article 105630.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chilyouth.2020.105630>

Wang, Y., Tian, L., & Huebner, E. S. (2019). Basic psychological needs satisfaction at school, behavioral school engagement, and academic achievement: Longitudinal reciprocal relations among elementary school students. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 56, 130-139.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2019.01.003>

Way, N., Reddy, R., & Rhodes, J. (2007). Students' perceptions of school climate during the middle school years: Associations with trajectories of psychological and behavioral adjustment.

American Journal of Community Psychology, 40(3-4), 194-213.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10464-007-9143-y>

Xing, X., & Gordon, H. R. (2021). Mediating effects of school engagement between high school on-time completion and career and technical education. *Vocations and Learning*, 14(1), 1-21.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s12186-020-09252-2>

Yang, C., Sharkey, J. D., Reed, L. A., & Dowdy, E. (2020). Cyberbullying victimization and student engagement among adolescents: Does school climate matter? *School Psychology*, 35(2), 158-

169. <https://doi.org/10.1037/spq0000353>

Zacharia, M. G., & Yablon, Y. B. (2022). School bullying and students' sense of safety in school:

The moderating role of school climate. *European Journal of Psychology of Education*, 37,

903-919. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10212-021-00567-9>

Zhao, X., Lynch, J. G., & Chen, Q. (2010). Reconsidering Baron and Kenny: Myths and truths about mediation analysis. *Journal of Consumer Research*, 37(2), 197–206.

<https://doi.org/10.1086/651257>

Zynuddin, S. N., Kenayathulla, H. B., & Sumintono, B. (2023). The relationship between school climate and students' non-cognitive skills: A systematic literature review. *Heliyon*, 9(4),

Article E14773. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e14773>

DRAFT